

**DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH TRANSACTIONAL SPEAKING
SKILLS THROUGH PROJECT-BASED LEARNING AMONG IRRIGATION
STUDENTS**

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***Аннотация:** В настоящем исследовании рассматривается методика преподавания английского языка как иностранного, направленная на то, чтобы предложить эффективный подход к повышению уровня владения разговорной речью с помощью проектного обучения. Основная цель исследования - выяснить, эффективно ли проектное обучение развивает навыки разговорной речи у студентов первого курса.*

***Ключевые слова:** беседа как транзакция, проектное обучение, разговорные навыки*

***Abstract:** The present study investigates a teaching methodology for English as a foreign language, aiming to offer an effective approach to enhancing transactional speaking proficiency using Project-Based Learning. The main objective of the research is to examine whether project-based learning effectively teaches transactional speaking skills to first-year students.*

***Keywords:** talk as a transaction, Project-Based Learning, speaking skills.*

Sahar Samy El-Sadat El-Nashar highlighted the significance of language as a crucial means of communication, emphasizing the importance of speaking skills for language learners. Communication plays a vital role in expressing ideas and understanding others within the context of our communities. Moreover, Florez pointed out that speaking is a challenging yet vital skill for language learners. It involves an interactive process that encompasses producing, receiving, and processing information orally, contributing significantly to the creation of meaning in language communication. Hatala & Friesen (2002) categorized speaking skills as communicative and productive, encompassing tasks such as creating, obtaining, and managing information to achieve proficiency in the target language. Thornbury (2005) underscored that speaking is a multi-sensory activity, involving paralinguistic features like eye contact, facial expression, and body language. He emphasized the significance of speaking in second language learning, stating that clear and efficient communication in the second language contributes to a learner's success in various life phases. This perspective advocates allocating ample time in speaking classes for students to enhance their speaking skills.

According to Cater & Nunan teaching speaking holds a distinct role in language instruction. Historically, the focus leaned towards written language due to the perceived complexity of studying speaking. Only in the last two decades, speaking gained attention in teaching, learning, and testing, although the emphasis was not initially on the production of spoken discourse. Uzbek students encounter challenges in learning English, especially in oral proficiency. Low scores in English exams reflect their struggles, often stemming from difficulties in using accurate, fluent, and complex expressions. Additionally, a lack of interest further complicates the learning process. Speaking, crucial for communication, plays a pivotal role in determining English proficiency, particularly in an institute setting. Success in speaking skills is influenced not only by students' learning styles but also by the methods and strategies employed by lecturers in the classroom.

Language acquisition is not only about how well one can use the grammar and vocabulary aspects nonetheless it is all about the availability of spoken interaction in another language. Therefore, while teaching the English language applying communication and communication-based techniques, the social interaction among students develops as well as their motivation to better their speaking. The fluency and accuracy of students are valid at present as it is becoming challenging for them to apply in real-life situations. On the other hand, students are too shy to speak up and unable to communicate with everyone. Additionally, students with psychological knowledge learn languages faster as a psychological approach is less involved in teaching today. To solve such issues in learning a foreign language doing different tasks can better students' language learning at the same time their psychological connections to the English language. Tasks will be designed to develop their critical thinking and problem-solving skills as well as encourage them to present their inter and intra-personal skills in the class. Application of information gap tasks, opinion gap tasks, and reasoning gap tasks makes students collaborate individually and with the group. As a major problem, communicative competence will be boosted by focusing on task completion. All in all, in this research, all applicable interactive tasks of PBL can give a real chance for practicing the target language.

Considering all the aspects of this research, Project-Based Learning is found to be a very actual and essential method in both the learning and teaching process. This method highlights learning to communicate through interaction in the target language, introducing authentic texts to learning situations, enhancing the learner's personal experiences, and linking classroom language learning with language

activation outside the classroom. In the performance of this approach, language-integrated activities are accompanied to raise learners' consciousness about specific features of the task performance. Through these activities, communication problems can be overcome with the tasks organized to produce the sub-skills.

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